

Insight into Urban Renewal as a Strategic Remedy for the Built Environment in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Urban renewal is considered effective solutions for improving the environmental integrity and sustainability of the built environment. Urban renewal is a land renewal process which helps to regenerate an aging area. This process often involves demolition of old building structures relocation of businesses and people. It also brings new urban designs and new concepts to the targeted redevelopment areas. Frequent appraisal should be done to ensure everything is on the right track and appropriate plan adjustments should be applied to fill up any loophole spotted. This research gives better understanding on the impact of urban renewal as a panacea for built environment and helps people to make relevant adjustments where necessary.

Key words: Urban Renewal, Strategic Remedy, Built Environment

INTRODUCTION TO URBAN RENEWAL

Urban renewal is primarily the act of revitalizing a failing urban area in order to restore economic vitality and improve the safety of the area, although the urban renewal statute is flexible and can be used for development, as well as redevelopment. Understanding that redeveloping urban areas is much harder and more expensive than new development. Urban renewal, which is generally called urban regeneration or regeneration in the United Kingdom, is a program of land redevelopment in areas of moderate to high density urban land use. This takes place when the physical social economic characteristics of a rundown urban area have been rebuilt as part of a strategic plan to improve an area. Housing, industrial locations and dock side developments are typical regeneration projects. Urban regeneration typically goes beyond the development of the physical area of a location; it will tackle the social and economic activity there as well. Urban renewal are financed by both private and the public sector. It redefines what "Up-to-standard" means to both the general public and the people living in the redevelopment areas. Urban renewal also helps to maintain a suitable balance among the social, environmental, economic and cultural aspects to make sure all these dimensions are working harmoniously to enhance the sustainability of the redevelopment areas. Every move made during the renewal process of an area brings about positive and negative impacts on the people, environment, economy and existing social linkage. The term Built Environment refers to the structures, and infrastructure, that are made by man. This can include everything from simple housing to entire cities, and even man-made outdoor environments. Built environments provide the basic necessities for human life as we know it, and therefore must be functional and healthy for all. Finding this balance is a complicated and challenging process, and one that is consistently being refined. A built environment includes all structures created by people, including infrastructure elements like streets, sidewalks, water and sewer lines, and electric and other utilities. Human behaviour experts and city planners work to discover the most positive use of space for people. A single building can also be studied for its effectiveness. Commercial building designs are constantly changing layouts to better accommodate the business that takes place within the walls. Panacea is defined as a solution or a remedy for a particular situation. Urban renewal as a panacea for Built environment involves the relocation of businesses, the demolition of structures, the relocation of people, and the use of eminent domain (government purchase of property for public purpose) as a legal instrument to take private property for city-initiated development projects. This process is also carried out in rural areas, referred to as village renewal, though it may not be exactly the same in practice.

The rehabilitation of city areas by renovating or replacing dilapidated buildings with new housing, public buildings, parks, roadways, industrial areas, etc., often in accordance with comprehensive plans, referred primarily to public efforts to revitalize aging and decaying inner cities, although some suburban communities undertook such projects as well. Including massive demolition, slum clearance, and rehabilitation.

Fig. 1 Established Built Environment

Urban renewal has been seen by proponents as an economic engine and a reform mechanism, and by critics as a mechanism for control. It may enhance existing communities, and in some cases result in the demolition of neighbourhoods. Many cities link the revitalization of the central business district and gentrification of residential neighbourhoods to earlier urban renewal programs. Over time, urban renewal evolved into a policy based less on destruction and more on renovation and investment, and today is an integral part of many local governments, often combined with small and big business incentives.

Salient Features of urban renewal are:

- a) It is relatively large-scale.
- b) It aims at improving the overall urban environment instead of solely providing specific facilities or replacing individual buildings.
- c) It normally involves properties in fragmented ownership, certain degree of Government participation like resumption is usually involved.
- d) It aims at achieving comprehensive planning gains.
- e) It incurs financial costs and a degree of social disruption.

History of Urban Renewal

The concept of urban renewal as a method for social reform emerged in England as a reaction to the increasingly cramped and unsanitary conditions of the urban poor in the rapidly industrializing cities of the 19th century. The agenda that emerged was a progressive doctrine that assumed better housing conditions would reform its residents morally and economically. Urban renewal has been operative since humans first built permanent settlements. "Following the progress of history and the passage of time, old cities are in a constant process of metamorphosis and unavoidably have to face the necessity of continuous regeneration" [1]. However, not until the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries did relatively coordinated efforts on the part of local governments, reform groups and business interests arise whose intent was to eliminate the physical manifestations of urban decline [2].

The renewal of Paris by Haussmann is thought to be the first large scale urban renewal project implemented. However, the United States was among the first countries to develop specific national programs of urban renewal [3]. The problem of deteriorating urban neighbourhoods have been recognized in the United States since the mid-nineteenth century and over the years, major efforts have been made to counteract decay and to rejuvenate cities throughout the country [4].

Problems Encountered by Existing Built Environment

There must be certain features in a built environment that makes it require renewal or redevelopment. These features vary based on the location of the environment. They are:

- a) **Pollution:** Pollution of air, water and soil require millions of years to recover. Industry and motor vehicles exhausts are the number one pollutants. Heavy metals, nitrates, plastic, oil spills, acidic rain, urban runoff are other forms of pollution.

Fig. 2 Air Pollution

Fig. 3 Polluted Water

- b) **Overpopulation:** The population of the planet is reaching unsustainable levels as it faces shortage of resources, water, fuels and food. Population explosion in less developed and developing countries are straining the already scarce resources.

Fig. 4 Over Populated Class Room

Fig. 5 Starvation of Children

- c) **Natural resource depletion:** Natural resource depletion is another crucial current environmental problem. Fossil fuel consumption results in emission of greenhouse gases responsible for global warming and climate change. Globally, people are taking efforts to shift to renewable sources of energy.

- d) **Waste disposal:** The overconsumption of resources and creation of plastics are creating a global crisis of waste disposal. Developed countries are notorious for producing an excessive amount of waste or garbage and dumping their waste in the oceans and less developed countries. Nuclear waste has serious health risks associated with it.

Fig. 6 Improper Disposal of Waste

- e) **Climate change:** Climate change occurs as a result of global warming. This occurs as a result of increase in temperature of the atmosphere by burning of fossil fuels and release of harmful gases by industries. Climate change has various harmful effects, not just melting of polar ice, change in seasons, frequent floods and occurrence of new diseases.
- f) **Loss of biodiversity:** Human activity is leading to the extinction of species and habitat and loss of bio-diversity. Eco systems which took millions of years to perfect, are in danger when any species population is decimating. Balance of natural processes like pollination is crucial to the survival of the eco system and ultimately the human race.

Fig. 7 Decrease in Population of Aquatic Animals

Fig. 8 Burning of Habitat of Terrestrial Animals

- g) **Deforestation:** Forests are natural sinks of carbon dioxide and produce fresh oxygen as well as helps in regulating temperature and rainfall. At present, forests cover 30% of the land, but every year tree cover is lost. Deforestation simply means clearing of green cover and making the land available for residential and industrial purposes.

Fig. 9 Deforestation

- h) **Urban sprawl (Migration):** This is the movement of people from areas of low population density to places of high population. This results in land degradation, increased traffic, environmental issues and health issues.

- i) **Health issues:** The current environmental problems pose a lot of risk to health of humans, and animals. Dirty water is the biggest health risk of the world and poses threat to the quality of life and public health. Runoff to rivers carries along toxins, chemicals and diseases carrying organisms. Pollutants cause respiratory diseases like Asthma and cardio-vascular problems.

Fig. 10 Health Effects of Population

Importance of Urban Renewal

Urban renewal is critical to the success of local communities and the long-term prosperity of citizens living in urban areas. Without urban renewal, there would be no incentive for developers to tackle the challenges associated with redevelopment, and our deteriorating downtown areas would be subject to increased crime and safety problems, while continued growth on the fringes of communities would add to the problem of urban sprawl. But thanks to the urban renewal, cities and towns across the state have been able to save older parts of town and make significant improvements to their communities. Importance can be itemized as:

- It improves the urban environment and infrastructure through the provision of more open space, community and other facilities.
- It also improves the urban layouts, road networks and other infrastructure.
- Replaces or renovates obsolete buildings.
- Thins out development and population densities to reduce the strain on overburdened transport and other infrastructure as well as makes available land to meet various uses such as housing needs.
- Better utilization of land.
- Speed up the redevelopment of neighbouring areas by private developers due to enhanced property values upon redevelopment of a particular area.

Urban Renewal Agents

There are a number of bodies which currently act as urban renewal agents or have done so in the past. They are:

- a) **Private developers:** they have been undertaking the great majority of urban redevelopment projects. Obviously, such projects are conducted for profit and therefore tend to result in higher development densities rather than thinning out. Also, private projects tend to be relatively smaller in scale, often focusing on single buildings with few improvements to layout and infrastructure. Nevertheless, the contribution of the private sector should not be underestimated. It is estimated that over half of the new private flats constructed in recent years have come from private redevelopment projects.
- b) **The Land Development Corporation (LDC):** was established in 1988 as the first dedicated urban renewal agency. The LDC was given only limited Government funding but was specifically given access to Government's resumption powers through the LDC Ordinance, provided it has taken all reasonable steps to acquire the properties affected by its projects by other means, including negotiating to purchase on terms that are fair and reasonable. This access to resumption powers is fundamental to the LDC's operations and is what enables it to attract private resources into urban renewal schemes.
- c) **The Housing Society:** This society has undertaken urban improvement schemes. These have been relatively small-scale focusing on the provision of additional and improved housing in urban areas rather than comprehensive urban renewal. Nevertheless, they are an important contribution to urban renewal generally.

Process Involved in Implementing Urban Renewal

There are several processes involved in the implementation of Urban Renewal to an environment. Approaches to sustainable development:

Global Economic Approach

Sustainable development is the entire combination of conditions and factors contributing to the maintenance or growth of incomes improved standard of living, well-being, its promotion thus depends on many aspects of economic activity and in particular control population growth, encouragement of technical change, optimal increase in the stock of factors contributing to the production of well-being, pricing of resources reflecting their relative scarcity, a change in the pattern of production and consumption in order to maintain the stock of scarce resources. Sustainability is the transmission or handling down of growth potential to future generations and in particular for the production of well-being.

Environmental or Ecological Approach

From ecological approach, 2 elements are compared in the stock of capital which enables the maintenance of the potential growth of well-being and that which must be transmitted to future generations. These include the stock of artificial capital or all the goods and factors of production created by human and natural capital or natural, renewable or non-renewable resources. On the basis of ecological approach to sustainable development the maintenance and transmission of a potential for growth and well-being require the application of management principles specific to each of these components of the overall capital each of which makes its own contribution to well-being.

Sustainable development should therefore ensure that this natural capital is safeguarded and transmitted to future generations and for several reasons:

- Certain resources are not renewable and are exhausted or lost immediately and this could lead to an extreme form of non-sustainability.
- Natural resources are sources of well-being by virtue of the amenities supplied such as aesthetic features of a site; leisure; factors for health etc.
- Natural capital constitutes the very substratum of economic growth to which it contributes directly.
- The existence of many uncertainties and in particular the possibilities for substitutions; irreversibility; the risks and thresholds of deterioration or exhaustion of resources; technical progress which would make it possible to compensate for the disappearance of certain natural resources; the taste and preferences of future generations.

People-Oriented Approach

The policy is aimed to balance the interests and needs of all sectors of the community and not to sacrifice the lawful rights of any particular group. The key elements of the Government's people-oriented approach to urban renewal include:

- Restructuring and re-planning designated older built-up areas, in particular the nine target areas.
- Designing more effective and environmentally-friendly local transport and road networks.
- Rationalising land uses which are incompatible with the surrounding areas.
- Redeveloping dilapidated buildings into new buildings of modern standard and environmentally-friendly design.
- Rehabilitating buildings in need of repair within the nine target areas.
- Redeveloping or revitalising under-utilised industrial areas.
- Preserving buildings, sites and structures of historical, cultural or architectural interest within the 200 priority project area and the nine target areas.
- Preserving as far as practicable the local characteristics of older neighbourhoods.
- Preserving the social networks of the local community.
- Providing purpose-built housing for groups with special needs, such as the elderly and the disabled.
- Providing more open space and community facilities.
- Enhancing the townscape with attractive urban design and by the provision of landscaping, open space and suitable street furniture.
- Providing adequate and affordable rehousing for tenants affected by URA's redevelopment projects.
- Providing fair and reasonable compensation to owners whose properties are resumed for the implementation of redevelopment projects.

Factors Affecting the Success of the Urban Renewal of an Environment

Challenges of urban renewal for sustainable urban development in Nigeria. Cities have to find out how to reduce the risks inherent in the tendency of contemporary urban societies to fall back on their heritage and roots as they face up to an identity crisis. This implies that innovation in urban space design represents an opportunity to construct a good identity of places and give an international scope to the urban form of cities [5].

The goal of environmental sustainability is to minimize environmental degradation which is the damage to the biosphere as a whole due to human activity. An unsustainable situation occurs when natural capital (the sum total of nature's resources) is used up faster than it can be replenished [6]. Sustainability requires that human activity, at a minimum, only uses nature's resources at a rate at which they can be replenished naturally.

However, there are a multitude of reasons why urban renewal in general specifically in the Nigeria cities and often not fully integrated into more traditional urban planning. Among the most important reasons are:

- i. **The Urbanization Process Itself [7]:** The rapid pace of urbanization places an enormous burden on the planning process i.e., planning for renewal, new development and upgrading of the existing urban environment.
- ii. **Urban Governance and Planning:** The negative impact of weak governance and the difficulty of transforming political will into action is a factor.
- iii. **The Structure of Urbanization:** The process and the resulting spatial form of urbanization is a function of many factors and are arguably different for each urban centre. With variations however, there is a general consensus that the process becomes more integrated as the urban center develops and the spatial form of growth can be broadly classified as concentric, sectional or multiple nuclei in form. In urbanizing Lagos metropolis the rapidly emerging new urban centers are primarily following the multiple nuclei development. This is particularly making urban renewal programme difficult.
- iv. **Lack of adequate framework:** the lack of adequate institutional and legal framework within which community safety and settlement strategies fit.
- v. **Institutional resistance:** the resistance to change and new approaches to tackling land use, crime sanitation and urban renewal process.
- vi. Lack of effective framework to ensuring truly inclusive participation and partnership in the development and delivery of sustainable community safety strategies and interventions. Such as: locally-based approach (defined neighbourhoods):
 - Citizen participation (residents, stakeholders)
 - Collaborative public-private partnerships (residents, corporations, community organizations, local government).
 - Comprehensive approach (problems are seen as interrelated across a range of issues and to include social economic and physical issues).
 - Consensus orientation, working in partnerships (rather than confrontation)
 - Community-building through partnerships.
- vii. **Lack of adequate information** on the value and place of urban renewal in urban planning [7].
- viii. **Public specific concerns** about development density, urban design (e.g., building height, local characteristics and public spaces), environmental protection and public transport considerations during the urban regeneration process.
- ix. **Emphasis on People-Centred Approach:** the relation between development and quality of life and the importance of preserving and revitalizing social network, local culture and heritage as well as local economy instead of cities physical renewal.
- x. **Compensation, Rehousing and Resumption:** Emphasis and expectation to offer owners and tenants more options of compensation and rehousing, like shop for shop and flat for flat rehousing in the same area. Social impact inability to expand the scope of social impact assessments look at both social benefits and social costs before and after the redevelopment.
- xi. **Expensive Cost of Renewal:** Urban renewal process is increasingly expensive as the redevelopment process involves not only building new structures but also resetting the original residents. At times the amount of compensation and relocation can reach 80-85% of the cost of redevelopment.
- xii. **Weak Groups:** Part of the population of the historic district in aging, poor and care should be provided both for affordable housing and public amenities.
- xiii. **Ownership:** The majority of the buildings is owned by corporations, both private and public or combinations. Small ownership is scarce making it unattractive for individuals to invest in improvements.
- xiv. **Lack of commitment** from community members and poor communication on the community participation process and this led to poor meeting attendance.

Urban sustainability can therefore be likened to an urban ecosystem which is referred as a composite of the natural environment, the built environment and the socio economic environment [7]. The land area and resources that must be used to sustain a population demands, sustainable utilization and management.

Pros and Cons of Urban Renewal

There are several advantages and disadvantages of urban renewal to an environment in as much as its relevance cannot be overemphasized.

The advantages of urban renewal are:

- **Economy:** Developing urban areas can result in new businesses, and existing companies usually experience an increase in business. Businesses follow population growth, especially in developing urban areas. For example, if a company builds or renovates a structure that houses a large number of employees, this may encourage new restaurants in that area to feed the company's employees. And other people besides the company's employers will also flock to this area to eat. The success of these companies encourages other types of businesses, such as dry cleaners, an automotive repair shop, a grocery and a drug store to consider moving to this location. As a result, the city's economy grows.

- **Transportation:** On one hand, placing many businesses in one location creates a pedestrian environment and reduces the need for cars. Compared to rural areas and suburbs, where it is often too far to walk from one location to the next, urban development places many businesses in close proximity to each other. On the other hand, cities like New York are famous for bumper-to-bumper traffic, since too many people crowded in small urban areas can create traffic congestion. Public transportation plays a major role in the success of many urban development areas.

Fig. 11 The Evolution of Transportation

- **Restoration:** Restoring crumbling or abandoned buildings and adding new structures can breathe life into what was once a dead and empty area. Abandoned buildings provide environments for criminal activity, such as drug use. Revitalizing these areas typically includes a ramped-up police presence, which can decrease the criminal element in urban areas. However, this is not always the case, and if crime is not sufficiently contained, consumers will not visit these urban areas, and business owners will close up shop and move to safer areas in the suburbs. This exodus leads to urban decay.
- **Residential housing:** In some instances, urban development requires moving tenants from their homes. These are often low-income residents who are forced to move to another location that may not provide them the convenient transportation that they once had. On the other hand, some urban development programs include rebuilding existing low-income housing and actually incorporating it with mid-income housing. On the other hand, housing in urban areas is considered a prime location and is usually much more expensive than housing in a rural or suburban areas.

Fig. 12 Public Housing Development

- **Quality of life:** The quality of life provided by urban development may vary from person to person. For instance, some urban dwellers may enjoy the excitement of city life, and living in close proximity to stores, museums and bars. They also enjoy the variety of people that they regularly come in contact with. However, some people may equate city excitement with noise, and prefer the quiet and the expansiveness of suburban living.

The disadvantages of urban renewal are:

- **Site Assembly:** This is the process of assembling small lots and individual properties in multiple ownership into larger lots capable of comprehensive redevelopment. This problem results from the fact that units in many multi-storey buildings are in separate ownership, so that anyone wishing to redevelop has to acquire many separate legal interests. Even if he succeeds in acquiring the majority of such interests but fails to acquire the last one, the whole scheme may fail. In such circumstances, large scale redevelopment becomes difficult and financially risky.
- **Relocation:** This covers the need to relocate residents and businesses from properties which need to be redeveloped. The problem of relocating tenants in rented accommodation in old buildings is in many ways one of the most difficult aspects of urban renewal. Owners may sell their properties to the developer at a price with which they are satisfied, often after difficult and protracted negotiations. Some will sell with vacant possession but many will not. Developers who acquire properties must therefore negotiate with the tenants to obtain vacant possession.
- **Viability:** The value of the redeveloped properties is not always sufficient to cover the costs of acquiring existing properties, relocation and development. The viability problem increases as fewer low-rise areas remain to be redeveloped and attention focuses on medium-rise properties. The costs of acquiring such properties and relocating residents are higher, while the development gains from redevelopment are less. There are large areas where urban renewal is needed now but where the development potential is insufficient to cover the cost (much less generate a profit) because of the need to reduce development densities. Change to a more valuable land use (e.g. from residential to commercial) and upgrading of the quality of accommodation may help to make projects more viable in some cases. However, such changes, if applied widely, mean the replacement of large numbers of affordable urban area flats with commercial property or more expensive flats.
- **Government Interference:** history reveals that governmental assistance has been accompanied by, or has in effect constituted, governmental intervention. Some degree is understandable, once the decision has been made to assist. The government no less than a private investor, desires an accounting of its funds and must establish rules designed to lessen the risk.
- **Housing Laws:** Our housing laws, initiated during a period of general economic depression are regarded by some as incompatible with current conditions. Public housing is administered to the Redevelopment and Housing Authority under the state laws governing such operations. Contracts and agreements made with Federal Public Housing Authority must be honoured.
- **The Moral And Social Effect of Public Housing:** there is evidence that public housing is characterized by a confusion in its basic objectives, that it has fostered restrictions upon the earning and initiative of its occupants, that it has deterred the production of rental housing by private industry, and that it has permitted the growth of power hierarchies in the form of public housing management. The claims of the public housers that public housing eliminates slums, that it houses low-income families who could otherwise not afford decent housing, that it reduces crime, juvenile delinquency and other antisocial behaviour are questioned. The impact of Urban Renewal on Societies

There are several aspects that cover the impact of urban renewal to a society. They include social, economic, environmental impacts.

Social Impact

- **Impact on transportation:** There is no great difference after the commencement of the redevelopment Project. Traffic is still busy as usual. The traffic is still acceptable because the improvement of the area did not reduce the population of the area, if at all it increases its population.
- **Impact on social linkage and collective memory:** the redevelopment might bring about positive impacts to the community and push forward district development, however it also leads to loss of collective memory. It doesn't however weaken the social linkage between neighbours, friends or families.
- **Impact on shopping behaviour and usage of community service:** most of the shops and venues utilized by the townies before redevelopment would no longer be there after development. As such, this leads to a sense of loss of iconic places and shops for people. Development is important but collective memory is also an important part of life.
- **Impact on housing choice:** Regarding housing choice, people have great concern on property price, transportation convenience and shopping areas. Before the announcement of the Redevelopment Project, they might have a plan to move to some new developed districts in the New Territories due to better environment, better air quality, lower housing price or rent, higher privacy and larger space. However, those areas are too far away from other people and the transportation is not very convenient in those districts and might sometimes be too far away from their work place.

Environmental Impact

- **Impact on air quality:** The air in the district becomes worse Redevelopment Project. Some of the people are suffering from allergy, the poorer air quality actually worsen their allergy condition, however, this is expected to be a short-term impact, the degree of impact shall become weaker near the end of the construction project. And in the long run after the redevelopment project completes, the new design would help better the air quality in the district. In other words, “the Bitter must come before the sweet; and that also make the sweet the sweeter”.
- **Impact on the building maintenance issues:** Many of the buildings have already deteriorated and become vacant while some of the roads are not levelled and could easily cause danger to residents and pedestrians. Many buildings in such areas are very old and many diseases can be easily found in these buildings. Moreover, water leakage and seepage problem plus drainage pipe blockage are also frequent problems occurring in the old buildings. This is not just a problem affecting the people living in these problematic buildings but also causing unnecessary risks to shoppers or visitors walking by these places. It is the duty of our government to protect our valuable lives and should urge the redevelopment progress to move forward smoothly at a faster pace. Moreover, there is always an insufficient supply of residential and commercial buildings in these rural areas, building more A-Grade commercial buildings or mixed commercial/residential buildings might help minimize this inadequate supply problem too.

Economic Impact

- **Impact on retail / business operation:** During any Redevelopment Project, many shops are either closed or relocated to other districts. Shops located near construction site, the extra dust generated during construction affects the hygiene level in the shops. To maintain the in-store hygiene at an acceptable to high standard level, one has to increase the frequency of in-store cleaning service. This has actually deepened the difficulty of human resources arrangement. Shortage of manpower has already been a problem for years in the retailing industry, so even a slight change on staff arrangement may exert great impact on the business. Moreover, due to the temporary arrangement in transportation, there is also impact on the product delivery arrangement. Travel time might be longer on some of the days during the construction period. Some of the supplier might request for additional transportation charge because of this, which might again lead to a slight increase in store expenses. Despite the problem of poorer air quality, there is also noise problem during the initial stage of the construction period.
- **Impact relating to business relocation:** Despite the above impacts on shop operation, another major concern brought to businessman is the possibility of shop relocation. Many clients worry about whether shop relocation is a must. They can choose to retire or find a new location in the same district to continue their business. The few things they worry about are whether the compensation they get can help cover the existing high rent or high property price plus whether they can find a location suitable for setting up their business again. There is also a small portion of shop owners who choose to take a rest during the redevelopment period, and plan to start business again when the whole project is done. For this group of people, they seem to be optimistic to the days when the redevelopment project completes, however, they also worry that even for the same or similar shop location, the rent and price will be much higher than that before redeveloped making life more difficult for them. Tenants of previous shops seem to be experience greater obstacles. First, as they are tenants and not owners of the shops, the compensation they get is much less. The compensation they get is not enough for them to restart their business in other location as rent is too high now. Some clients are capable of affording the rent of a new place; however, they already lost the existing client base and have to re-build a new client base. As this act takes time, some of them have chosen to lengthen opening hours to gather more business opportunities; however, this does not always work. Moreover, prolonged work has actually incurred other problems like reduction of family communication and health problems.

Long Term Implication of Urban Renewal

Urban renewal sometimes lives up to the hopes of its original proponents – it has been assessed by politicians, urban planners, civic leaders, and residents – it has played an undeniably important role. Additionally, urban renewal can have many positive effects. Replenished housing stock might be an improvement in quality; it may increase density and reduce sprawl; it might have economic benefits and improve the global economic competitiveness of a city's centre. It may, in some instances, improve cultural and social amenity, and it may also improve opportunities for safety and surveillance.

Long-Term Implications on Social Linkage

Social linkage is one of the important components of social capital. As mentioned before, there is always value embedded in “social capital”, that is, the relationships among people and the networks they form. The distortion of our “social capital” or existing social fabric and networks through massive building demolition and displacement of existing residents may lead to social isolation. Its impact on social linkage of people living or working in such areas seem not greatly affected.

Another element which might affect “social capital” is the collective memory of a society, that is, a group memory that exists outside of and lives beyond an individual [8]. People generally agree that collective memory is an important

element which possesses a lifelong impact on an individual, however, they also agree that it is important for a society to continue to move forward and develop. The key observation concluded from this part is whether there are alternatives for the “collective memory” lost.

Long-Term Impact related to Population Displacement & Gentrification

Gentrification is the class transformation of urban neighbourhoods that were revalorized by previous rounds of disinvestment and outmigration amidst metropolitan growth and suburbanization. Class transformation is rooted in long-run changes in the social and technical division of labour, distribution of income, wealth and educational opportunities.

One of the positive impact related to gentrification is that redevelopment of a district often brings about new housing development, new shops and restaurants, and new, higher-wage jobs. It might also bring about a boost on number of jobs particularly in the service and construction sector. However, planners and stakeholders should always be careful and sensitive at this point, gentrification and population displacement could lead to imbalance of a society if it is not treated appropriately, and there are also several other impacts of greater concern in residents’ eyes.

It provides various types of allowances and re-housing arrangement for affected tenants and owners. Such population relocation arrangement might further impact on the business environment in the district. As people are relocated to other districts, the original customer flow will be reduced and so as the demand for goods and services in the district.

Expectations on Urban Redevelopment

People’s expectation on urban doesn’t differ tremendously. Most people generally believe that urban redevelopment could help improve their living quality, which often helps to clear up dilapidated areas in a district, review and change existing spatial arrangement, reconstruct various infrastructures, provide buildings of better quality, create job opportunities and boost business development in the district. Another favourable result of district redevelopment is a remarkable upgrading of economic activities in the neighbourhood.

Limitations of Urban Renewal

The objective of urban renewal is to shape the public realm of cities to maximise the benefits, explicitly or implicitly, for particular sets of people within some concept of the public interest. In order to achieve this, certain actions must be put in place, and these actions would have boundaries as to what or the extent urban renewal can change a place. These Limitations include the following:

The Nature Of The Public Realm

The public realm is an ambiguous term. It deals with both the public aspects of the physical world that one inhabits and with the world of ideas that is subject to public scrutiny. While a significant portion of cities – much of its infrastructure and open spaces – is in public ownership and might be considered to simply be the public realm, it is not quite as easy as that. The interior of public buildings and places such as school playgrounds are not necessarily open to the public and there is much quasi-public space (such as the interiors of shopping arcades and shopping malls) that is.

While the narrower focus of urban renewal is on the ground floor of cities, its use and appearance, much is affected by the uses of the adjacent buildings and of the third (and, indeed, the fourth) dimensional quality of built environments. While the façades and entrances of buildings are privately owned in capitalist societies, their location and appearance very much affects the public’s perception of the world and so are frequently deemed to be subject to public control. Extending the concept even further, access to light and sunlight very much affects the quality of life of people and it is deemed to be in the public interest to provide access to them. What then is ‘in the public interest’?

The Nature of the Public Interest

Urban designers have taken the stance that their work is in the public interest [9]. Yet one can differentiate between the public interest and the public’s interest. The former is deemed to be based on some model of what is good for people and the second is based on what people say is good for themselves. Using the former definition it is easy if one, as many people have done, falls into the trap of a ‘give-’em-what-I-think is-good-for-them attitude’. An alternative position that has been taken is ‘to-give-’em-what-they-say-they-want’. The latter tends to be the politician’s attitude.

The position taken here is that neither approach is satisfactory. It is in the public interest to bring to the public’s attention ways of doing things that they had not thought of before. Such knowledge must, however, be based on an empirical understanding of the range of human behaviours and values. It must also represent the interests of diverse segments of the community – young and old, rich and poor – within different geographic and cultural settings. Urban renewal decisions are ultimately made in the political arena and the power of an argument depends on the quality of the evidence used.

The Nature of Urban Renewal: The Lessons from Experience

In recent times, it is now being used loosely to refer to individual buildings and landscape designs built in cities, as such it signifies almost nothing. Urban designing is indeed an activity that overlaps many others but can one can identify a number of types of design that, if nor unique amongst the professional design fields, are central to what can be regarded

as urban design practice. It is possible to distinguish amongst urban design as: 1) Urban Physical Policy Formulation, 2) Infrastructure Design, 3) Piece-by-Piece Urban Design, and 4) Total Urban Design [10-11].

CONCLUSION

As urban development deals with mainly infrastructural development and social amenities which cannot eliminate the long lasting beliefs which exist mentally within the society, as stories would be told, different locations might be fought by the communities so as it remains the way it is for cultural and sentimental beliefs. No matter the effect Urban Renewal makes to a society, it cannot change the mind-set of the urbanites in the renewed environment.

Urban renewal has been responsible for the rehabilitation of communities—as well as displacement. Replacement housing – particularly in the form of housing towers – might be difficult to police, leading to an increase in crime, and such structures might in themselves be dehumanising. Urban renewal is usually non-consultative. Urban renewal continues to evolve as successes and failures are examined and new models of development and redevelopment are tested and implemented.

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